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De: Editorial Office <vaccines@mdpi.com>
Para: Manuel Grana <manuel.grana@ehu.es>
Cc: Manuel Graña <manuel.grana@ehu.es>
Asunto: [Vaccines] Manuscript ID: vaccines-2155852 – Submission Received

Dear Professor Graña,

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Journal name: Vaccines
Manuscript ID: vaccines-2155852
Type of manuscript: Article
Title: Legitimate questions on “Real-World Immunogenicity and Reactogenicity of Two Doses of Pfizer-BioNTech COVID-19 Vaccination in Children Aged 5–11 Years”
Authors: Manuel Graña *
Received: 27 December 2022
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Submitted to section: COVID-19 Vaccines and Vaccination,
https://www.mdpi.com/journal/vaccines/sections/COVID-19_vaccines_vaccination

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If you have any questions, please do not hesitate to contact the Vaccines editorial office at vaccines@mdpi.com

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